

CONCEPT OF “KINDNESS” IN THE MODERN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE IMAGE

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Annotation: The article is about phraseology, which is connected with other subjects such as history, literature, country study, and other subjects of linguistics- lexicology, semantics, grammar, phonetics, stylistics, history of language, etymology, text linguistics and general linguistics. In article also it is analyze the concept “Kindness” in Uzbek by the help of phraseological dictionaries.

Key words: phraseology, phraseological units, concept “Kindness”, etymology.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена фразеологии, которая связана с другими предметами, такими как история, литература, страноведение, и другими предметами лингвистики - лексикологией, семантикой, грамматикой, фонетикой, стилистикой, историей языка, этимологией, лингвистикой текста и общим языкознанием. В статье также анализируется понятие “доброта” в узбекском языке с помощью фразеологических словарей.

Ключевые слова: фразеология, фразеологические единицы, концепт “Доброта”, этимология.

Kindness and compassion are considered to be instrumental buffers for the negative effects of stress, thought to be perpetuated by strengthening positive interpersonal connections. Several studies have demonstrated these effects in the clinical setting, with kindness being shown to elicit elevation in mood, increase in altruism, and the promotion of connection to others.

What is Kindness?

Kindness is considered to be a form of positive social connection which is shown to buffer stress via multifactorial mechanisms. Positive interpersonal connexion is produced as a consequence of pro-social behavior, for example, donations, volunteerism, and providing social support. alternative descriptions of kindness include compassion, generosity, and care, among other related terms. Through engagement in pro-social behavior, happiness is induced, which in turn, can reinforce continued pro-social behavior.

As part of the effect of prosocial behavior, is the induction of other-praising moral emotion, a term which describes the feelings of positivity generated when witnessing authors engage in

virtuous acts such as generosity, selflessness, love, and kindness. Uplifting feelings physical sensations, including warmth and tearfulness.

At the dictionary level of the language construction there are lexical and phraseological layers. Phraseology is derived from the Greek word phraseology, meaning phrase, turn of speech, knowledge, concept, logos-science, doctrine. Phraseology is divided into two types:

1. A stable word combination inherent in a language is a set of phrase.
2. It is section of linguistic that studies stable vocabulary and phrases inherent in a language.

Phraseology is a Pearl of language. The reflects the peculiarities of the history and culture of the people. In phraseologisms, the bright National features of the people are embodied. English phraseology is rich and its history is long. In this is considered from the outside among from the outside among pure English phraseologisms, that is, international phraseologisms are also numerous. Phraseology is an extremely complex phenomenon and its study is subject to a specific style, and also requires study with reference to a number of other disciplines such as lexicology, linguistics, Stylistics, phonetics, history, logical and textology.

The science of phraseology is associated with such as subjects as lexicology, semantics, phonetics, Stylistics, history of language, etymology, Text Linguistics and general linguistics, among others, the science of history, literature and Linguistics. Phraseology consist of words, and the word is the main object by which lexicology studies. Besides on the sources of lexicology, it is possible to determine the nature of phraseological components, as well as their linguistic level. The theory of the lexical meaning of a word developed in semantics help to determine the linguistic nature of phraseology and distinguish its meaning in the composition of phraseology.

The word in phraseology has always lost its morphological features, it turns out that morphology helps to determine what is lost or preserved in this area.

In the development of a general system of studying phraseology, a specialist in the field (phraseologist) uses the experience of General Linguistics. In turn, the object of phraseology is so complex and peculiar that in the process of its study it creates new resources for the development of the above-mentioned linguistic Sciences. For example:

- **do someone a kindness- *kingadir mehribonlik qilish.***

to do a kind deep for a person. *My neighbor did me a kindness when he cut my grass. I am always happy to have the opportunity of doing someone a kindness.*

- **kill someone with kindness – *kingadir juda katta mehribonlik qilish.***
- Fig. to be enormous kind to someone. **You are just killing me with kindness. Why? Don't kill them with kindness.**
- **kill somebody with kindness – *kingadir xaddan ortiq mehribonlik qilish.***

To be kind to someone Rob`s killing me with kindness – he phones me all the time to see if I`m alright when really I just need to be left alone.

- **milk of human kindness – ta`biyy mehrimonlik va boshqalarga xayrixohlik.**
Fig. natural kindness and sympathy shown to others. (From Shakespeare`s play Macbeth, I. v.) *Mary is completely hard and selfish – she doesn`t have the milk of human kindness in her. Roger is too full of the milk of human kindness and people take advantage of him.*
- **the milk human kindness (literary)- boshqalarga mehrimon bo`lish.**

Being good and kind to other people.

Usage note: this phrase come from Shakespeare`s play “Macbeth”.

She`s one of those amazing people who`s just overflowing with the milk of human kindness.

- **kill somebody with kindness- boshqa odamga mehrimon bo`ib xoxlayotgan narsasiga erishmoq.**
to get what you want by being very kind to another person while most coaches can be very tough, ours kills his players with kindness.

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